

**FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR AND DAMAGE
DEVELOPMENT IN WOVEN FABRIC
AND HYBRID FABRIC COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

Two eight shaft satin weave fabrics made from carbon fibres and aramid fibres were investigated together with an interwoven hybrid fabric of the same style, with 50 % carbon and 50 % aramid fibres. The matrix system used was the type 934. For comparison, also test results of a symmetrical laminate with continuous fibres and a stacking sequence of $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]$ will be given. The matrix material used was in this case the epoxy MY 720.

All the material selected was investigated with respect to their static and fatigue properties. Special attention was given to examine the damage development by means of initiation and growth of internal cracking, delaminations and fibre fractures. X-radiographs and scanning electron microscopy were extensively used to evaluate the damage mechanisms occurring.

INTRODUCTION

Woven fabric composite materials are gaining increasing importance in the application for engineering purposes. Major structural parts and components are designed with this material, which has advantages in easy handling and formability by satisfactory mechanical properties. Besides its broad technical use the understanding of the material behaviour as well as damage propagation and its failure mechanisms remain

quite uncertain [1,2] Hybrids, a composite material consisting of two different types of fibres, which together with the surrounding matrix form the composite, promise to spread the composite material properties to a more balanced behaviour. Therefore, hybrid composites focus more and more attention. However, this type of material has not yet reached a broad technical use, and - from a scientific point of view - its mechanical behaviour is not satisfactorily understood [3].

Woven fabrics consist of two sets of intrerlaced threads, the warp and the fill. The types of fabrics can be identified by the repeating patterns. Two geometrical parameters can be defined to characterise a fabric: n_{fg} denotes that a warp thread is interlaced with every n_{fg} -th fill thread and n_{wg} denotes that a fill thread is interlaced with every n_{wg} -th warp thread. In most cases $n_{wg} = n_{fg} = n_g$. Fabrics with $n_g = 2$ are known as plain weaves, $n_g = 4$ as "crowfoot" and fabrics with $n_g > 4$ having isolated interlaced regions are known as satin weaves. In the case of hybrid fabrics the pattern of arrangement of fibre types in the fill direction repeats for every two warp threads and that pattern in the warp direction repeats for every two fill threads. Hybrid fabrics consist of two material types denoted as α and β -threads. Fig. 1 is a schematic of an 8-harness ($n_g = 8$) hybrid fabric.

Fig.1:
Schematic of an 8-harness hybrid woven fabric

The static and fatigue response of a satin weave fabric has partly been reported in [2,4] while for a hybrid fabric only some static data were published in [5]. In the present study a comprehensive view of the static and fatigue properties and

the damage mechanisms occurring in composites made of carbon and aramid fibre fabrics and a balanced hybrid fabric of the same type of fibres, is given. The results will be compared with non-woven material.

MATERIALS AND TESTING

Laminates were moulded from both woven and non-woven pre-impregnated sheets of high-strength carbon fibres and aramid fibres. The laminates with continuous fibres had an MY 720 based epoxy resin (Ciba - Geigy) and HTA fibres (Toho-Beslon). The fabric was a balanced 8-harness satin weave in a 934 epoxy resin from Fiberite Corporation. For the carbon fabric T300 fibres from Toray and for the aramid fabric Kevlar-49 (Du Pont) fibres were used. For the hybrid fabric 50 % aramid and 50 % carbon fibres were used. Since one prepreg sheet of woven material was approximately twice as thick as a ply of non-woven material, and each sheet of cloth was thus similar to two plies of non woven unidirectional prepreg stacked at 90° to each other as in a (0,90) lay up.

Symmetrical laminates were produced with a stacking sequence of $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ for both the continuous and the aligned discontinuous non-woven laminates reaching a final thickness of 2 mm. The sheets produced from woven fabric consisted of eight layers and were 15-20 per cent thicker than the non-woven laminates. This difference in thickness was mainly due to the lower fibre volume fraction of the woven carbon fibre laminates. Since the volume fraction was slightly different in all types of laminate, no correction has been made in the data, since it was felt to be more relevant to compare the materials as made.

Tensile tests were carried out on 200 mm long coupons with the fill fibres parallel to the 0° load direction in the 0° , 90° woven layer and with the 0° fibres parallel to the load direction in the non-woven laminates. The width of the coupons was between 16-25 mm. Fatigue tests were performed in

a servo-hydraulic test machine with a stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ and a frequency of 10 Hz.

RESULTS

The static properties of each of the laminates used are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties from static tests

	Laminate: Continuous Fibres	Fabric: Carbon Fibres	Aramid Fibres	Hybrid
σ_f [MPa]	850	645	490	470
E [GPa]	78	68	30	50
ϵ_f [%]	1.3	0.96	1.66	0.96

In the cross-ply laminate with the continuous fibres a very high fracture stress, σ_f , is reached due to the superior properties of the carbon fibres. In the fabric the lower volume fraction of fibres and undulation of fibre threads lead to a reduction of the fracture stress of about one third, while in the fabric with the aramid fibres the fracture stress is again reduced, as a result of their lower strength. The modulus of elasticity, E, shows the same dependence on the type of laminate or fibre chosen. The strain to failure, ϵ_f , reaches the strain properties of the carbon fibres in the case of the laminate. In the fabric, failure of fibre bundles preferentially occurs when the threads in the warp and fill direction are interlaced, leading to a comparatively low fracture strain. In the case of the aramid fibres the failure strain is significantly higher due to the higher failure strain of the fibres itself. In the hybrid fabric the modulus of elasticity is determined by the rule of mixtures, but the fracture stress is determined by the low fracture strain of the carbon fibres, which reaches in the hybrid exactly the same value as in the carbon fabric.

The general sequence of damage accululation under monotonic loading in tension is that transverse cracks form in the 90° plies, their density increases to a saturation level referred to as the Characteristic Damage State [8]. While this behaviour was observed in cross-ply laminates with continuous fibres the fabric exhibited only few transverse cracks and no regular crack pattern could be observed. This is shown in Fig., 2a, which is on X-radiograph from a broken tensile test specimen. However, on the case of the aramid fibre an hybrid composites it turned out, that here numerous transverse cracks and additionally longitudinal cracks were formed (Fig. 2b, c). But it was found, that some of the cracks had already been present in the virgin specimen.

Fig 2: X-radiographs with transverse cracks developed during static loading for 8-harness woven fabrics; a) Carbon fibres; b) Aramid fibres; c) Hybrid

The fatigue behaviour of the different laminates investigated is summarized in Fig. 3; the maximum stress level in each fatigue load cycle, σ_{\max} , is plotted versus the number of cycles to failure, N_F . The cross-ply laminate can sustain the highest number of load cycles at the highest stress levels with a very small slope of the Wöhler-curve. The endurance limit is reached at about $\sigma_e \approx 670$ MPa. The Wöhler-curve of the fabric with carbon fibres has a comparatively steep slope, reaching the endurance limit at about 420 MPa, while

the aramid fabric seems to react more sensitive against fatigue loading, having an endurance limit of about 300 MPa. In the hybrid fabric the endurance limit is only slightly higher.

Fig. 3: Variation of peak stress level for failure with number of cycles to failure for the laminates investigated

During fatigue cycling, stiffness reduction was used as an analogue to monitor damage development. Its change can be directly related to stress redistribution which is to be expected if internal damage occurs in a composite laminate. A typical stiffness reduction curve for the cross-ply laminate is shown in Fig. 4. The shape of the curve suggests three regions of interest, and it has been shown in previous publications [6,7] that typical damage mechanisms can be related to each stage. In the woven fabric reinforced with carbon fibres, which is also shown in Fig. 4, the initial stiffness reduction in early fatigue life is followed by a smaller region with a gradual reduction. While in the cross-ply laminate final failure did initiate abruptly (sudden death behaviour) within the last few per cent of fatigue life, in the fabric after about 50 per cent of fatigue life a further pronounced decrease in stiffness occurs which is shown up by the stepwise stiffness reduction in the second half of the fatigue life. In the hybrid fabric these three different damage

Fig. 4: Normalized stiffness reduction (E/E_0) versus fatigue life for the cross-ply laminate and the 8-harness satin fabric, both reinforced with carbon fibres

regions can hardly be distinguished (Fig. 5). In general the stiffness reduction curve is rather steep, only at the very beginning and at the end of fatigue life some sudden stiffness reduction can be found. However for the fabric with aramid fibres the stiffness remained constant, until the end of fatigue life a sudden drop occurred during the last few load cycles.

Fig. 5: Normalized stiffness reduction (E/E_0) versus fatigue life for the hybrid fabric reinforced with both aramid and carbon fibres

The damage mechanisms in the cross-ply laminate have already been described in the literature [6,7]. In the fabric composite transverse cracks are initiated during early fatigue. Cracks develop along the transverse threads in the warp direction (Fig. 6). In the undulated region, where a fill thread

Fig. 6:
X-radiograph taken near the end
of fatigue life of a carbon
fibre 8-harness satin fabric

encircles a warp thread, a lower stiffness than in the surrounding regions with straight threads is present. This lower stiffness causes a local softening and the maximum strain appears at the center of undulation and initiates the transverse cracks [9]. Later longitudinal cracks develop along the warp threads and increase both in length and density. A similar mechanism as described elsewhere for the cross-ply laminates [6,7] causes this longitudinal crack growth; the fill threads contract because of tensile loading. This contraction is hindered by the warp threads. Stresses of a tensile nature appear between the fill threads, whereas the warp threads are under a compression load in the fibre direction.

At the undulation of warp and fill threads delaminations develop in the interior (dark areas between longitudinal cracks in Fig. 6) being initiated at cross sections of transverse and longitudinal cracks, where local tensile stresses are provided by the transverse warp threads. As soon as delaminations occur the stiffness of a test coupon decreases considerably and enters the steep slope of the curve with the last 50 per cent of fatigue life before final failure.

Fig. 7 shows a delaminated area at a cross-section of a warp and fill thread in a CFRP-fabric. For the X-radiograph a gold chloride solution was used as an opaque. After the pyrolyzation of the matrix "debris" of the opaque remained on the now

Fig. 7:
SEM-micrograph of a pyrolyzed
carbon fibre 8-harness satin
fabric. Extension of an internal
delamination

bare fibres and the extension of the delamination could be detected by Scanning Electron Microcopy (SEM). Final failure initiates when the first fibre fracture occurs in the fill threads (Fig. 8a), at the center of undulation. Total failure of a fill thread (Fig. 8b) results in the stepwise stiffness reduction as documented in Fig.4.

Fig. 8: SEM-micrograph, pyrolyzed fabrics

- a) partly failed C-fibre thread, hybrid fabric
- b) totally failed C-fibre thread, carbon fibre fabric

CONCLUSION

Comparing the different kinds of laminates investigated, it is evident that the cross-ply laminate is less sensitive to fatigue loading than the fabrics. Within the fabrics the best

fatigue properties are achieved when carbon fibres are used as reinforcement and the worse with aramid fibres.

The final failure process can be indicated quite early, after about 50 per cent of the fatigue life, by an increasing slope of the stiffness reduction curve arising from the development of longitudinal crack growth and interior delaminations at the undulation of warp and fill threads. Failure of 0^0 fibres and single threads occurs. The strength and stiffness of the test coupons is reduced gradually until final failure.

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